

*Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology
Systems (FOWTs)*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MARINEWIND project aims to identify challenges and potential opportunities for enhancing the role of floating offshore wind technology in innovative system integration solutions. The project will explore market dynamics, policy and regulatory issues, social considerations, financial aspects, techno-economic solutions, and recommendations for storage and flexibility provisions.

This report presents the outcomes of the MARINEWIND 2nd Co-creation workshop in Portugal, organized on the 22nd of May 2024 in Viana do Castelo (north of Portugal). The event, held in Portuguese under the title "*Offshore wind energy auctions in Portugal - How to apply pre-qualification criteria to boost the supply chain and promote biodiversity and marine ecosystems in Portugal?*", gathered 25 participants from various sectors, including Industry, Scientific & Research, Public authorities, Civil society, Green innovation, and Policy/Regulatory.

Hosted at Navio Gil Eannes (a former hospital boat now transformed into a Museum) in collaboration with the City Hall of Viana do Castelo, the workshop addressed the challenges of floating offshore wind energy technology development. While cost remains a critical factor in offshore wind energy auctions, non-price criteria are increasingly recognized for their role in shaping future offshore wind farms. The workshop examined criteria suggested by the European Union and preliminarily defined by the Portuguese Government, focusing on environmental sustainability, promoting a circular economy with local supply chains, social and territorial development, and resilience criteria for key offshore equipment. Additionally, all participants contributed to identifying the main barriers and opportunities that exist in Portugal for the growth of floating wind in the country, considering social, environmental, technological, and financial aspects, by participating in the MARINEWIND Mentimeter questionnaire and discussing the results during the event.

The workshop promoted collaborative problem-solving between developers and fishermen associations to develop strategies for overcoming identified barriers and highlighted opportunities for growth in the sector. Additionally, the event served as a platform for knowledge sharing and networking among industry experts, stakeholders, and participants, encouraging the formation of partnerships and connections to advance floating offshore wind technology.

The results of these discussions will be incorporated into the MARINEWIND web-based Geographical Information System (webGIS). This system will offer customized information about Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWT) to stakeholders based on their category, location, and objectives. The system will also offer policy recommendations for informed Renewable Energy Sources (RES) policies and strategies to enhance societal acceptance (WP4). The Replicability Plan will facilitate the transfer of knowledge.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
TABLE OF FIGURES	5
1 EVENT DETAILS	6
2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS	10
2.1 RELEVANCE OF THE TOPICS ADDRESSED IN THE 2ND WORKSHOP IN PORTUGAL IN THE NATIONAL FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND CONTEXT	10
2.2 RESULTS OF THE PRESENTATION “APPLYING PRE-QUALIFICATION CRITERIA TO OFFSHORE WIND ENERGY AUCTIONS IN PORTUGAL TO BOOST THE SUPPLY CHAIN AND PROMOTE BIODIVERSITY AND MARINE ECOSYSTEMS IN PORTUGAL”	11
2.3 PRESENTATION OF THE EUROPEAN MARINEWIND PROJECT	14
3 CO-CREATION ACTIVITY	15
3.1 RESULTS OF THE SURVEY	15
QUESTION 1 - WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING CATEGORIES REPRESENTS YOU?	15
QUESTION 2 - WHAT ARE THE MOST IMPORTANT ENABLING FACTORS TO INVEST IN FOWTs?	16
QUESTION 3 - IN YOUR OPINION, WHICH OF THESE RISKS IS MOST SIGNIFICANT TO YOUR VALUE CHAIN?	16
QUESTION 4 - HOW CAN THE INDUSTRY ENGAGE WITH LOCAL COMMUNITIES AND STAKEHOLDERS TO ADDRESS CONCERNS RELATED TO THE DEPLOYMENT OF FOWTs? PRIORITISE THE ACTIONS.....	17
QUESTION 5 - WHAT ARE THE KEY ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERNS ASSOCIATED WITH FOWTs?	17
QUESTION 6 - WHAT INFRASTRUCTURE CHALLENGES NEED TO BE ADDRESSED TO SUPPORT THE GROWTH OF THE FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND ENERGY INDUSTRY?	18
QUESTION 7 - WHAT STRATEGIES CAN BE EMPLOYED TO BUILD TRUST AND ACCEPTANCE AMONG COMMUNITIES WHERE THESE TECHNOLOGIES ARE BEING DEPLOYED?.....	18
QUESTION 8 - WHICH ACTIVITY IS THE MOST CONFLICTING WITH THE OFFSHORE WIND SECTOR?	19
QUESTION 9 - WHICH ACTIVITY IS MOST COMPATIBLE WITH THE FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND SECTOR?	19
QUESTION 10 - WHAT KIND OF IMPACT DO YOU THINK FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND FARMS COULD HAVE ON LOCAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES (E.G., FISHING, TOURISM)?	20
QUESTION 11 - WHAT KIND OF IMPACT DO YOU THINK FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND FARMS COULD HAVE ON THE ENVIRONMENT (E.G., BIODIVERSITY)?	20

QUESTION 12 - DO YOU THINK THAT FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND FARMS COULD BRING BENEFITS TO THE LOCAL COMMUNITY (E.G., ECONOMIC BENEFITS AND ENERGY SAVINGS, IMPROVEMENT OF AIR QUALITY, GENERAL IMPROVEMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE)? 21

4 DISCUSSIONS TOPICS OVERVIEW22

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS23

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Initial target audience for the 2nd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (Viana do Castelo)..... 8

Figure 2. Participants of the 2nd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (Viana do Castelo). 9

Figure 3. MENTIMETER Tool Question 1 results. 15

Figure 4. MENTIMETER Tool Question 2 results. 16

Figure 5. MENTIMETER Tool Question 3 results. 16

Figure 6. MENTIMETER Tool Question 4 results. 17

Figure 7. MENTIMETER Tool Question 5 results. 17

Figure 8. MENTIMETER Tool Question 6 results. 18

Figure 9. MENTIMETER Tool Question 7 results. 18

Figure 10. MENTIMETER Tool Question 8 results. 19

Figure 11. MENTIMETER Tool Question 9 results. 19

Figure 12. MENTIMETER Tool Question 10 results. 20

Figure 13. MENTIMETER Tool Question 11 results. 20

Figure 14. MENTIMETER Tool Question 12 results. 21

1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Sea Centre Room, on the Gil Eannes Museum Ship – Viana do Castelo

EVENT DATE: 22nd May 2024 14:00-16:30

EVENT TITLE: Offshore wind energy auctions in Portugal - How can pre-qualification criteria be applied to boost the supply chain and promote biodiversity and marine ecosystems in Portugal?

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: None

LEAD ORGANISER: WavEC Offshore Renewables

LANGUAGE: Portuguese

CONCEPT: The workshop targeted to bring together industry leaders, experts, and stakeholders to discuss and explore effective market measures for the rapid expansion of floating offshore wind projects in Portugal through the analysis of pre-qualification criteria to be applied in the upcoming offshore wind energy auctions in Portugal, and the potential barriers and enablers of Floating Offshore Wind projects to be implemented. The event aimed to strengthen collaboration between industry, academia, authorities, and fishermen, to accelerate and ensure the secure advancement of the floating wind industry towards successful commercial implementation.

OBJECTIVES

The workshop's specific objectives were to address the challenges in auctioning floating offshore wind energy in Portugal, recognizing that while price remains a critical factor in offshore wind energy auctions, non-price criteria are increasingly influential in shaping future offshore wind farms. The workshop aimed to address the importance of these non-price criteria, focusing on environmental sustainability, the promotion of a circular economy with local supply chains, social and territorial development, and resilience criteria for key offshore equipment, as suggested by the European Union and preliminarily defined by the Portuguese Government. The workshop also aimed to identify the main barriers and opportunities for the growth of floating offshore wind in Portugal, considering social, environmental, technological, and financial aspects. Active participation and discussion were facilitated through the MARINEWIND Mentimeter questionnaire, allowing participants to share their insights and perspectives.

The 2nd Co-Creation workshop in Portugal was designed to contribute to the overall objectives of the MARINEWIND project:

- Increase awareness of FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Encourage social acceptance by directly involving local communities and fishermen and addressing environmental issues.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in the Portuguese MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The event targeted, in general, representatives of industry, research institutes, public authorities, supply chains, civil society (also Fishermen), green innovation and policy and regulatory entities involved in the floating offshore wind sector.

For each specific category, the initial targeted audience included participants from:

- Industry: technology and project developers.
- Supply chain: port infrastructure, cable design and installation, tech/project developers, and trade associations, O&M services.
- Scientific & research community.
- Public authorities: at national level and maritime transport authorities.
- Policy/Regulatory: regulatory bodies at national level.
- Civil society: civil society organisations, citizens, and fishermen organizations.
- Green innovation: SMEs, ecologists.

Apart from the general audience, for this workshop in particular, the targeted audience of civil society focused on the participation of fishermen and fishermen associations. Their representation was particularly valuable in this event because the floating offshore wind farm WindFloat Atlantic project is located 20 km from the coast of Viana do Castelo.

AGENDA:

14:00-14:30 Welcome coffee

14:30-14:45 Presentation of the European MARINEWIND project by Janete Gonçalves, Communication and Dissemination Coordinator of the project

14:45-15:15 Presentation "*Application of pre-qualification criteria in offshore wind energy auctions in Portugal to boost the supply chain and promote biodiversity and marine ecosystems in Portugal*", by Inês Machado, Marine Environment and Licensing Coordinator - WavEC Offshore Renewables

15:15-16:00 MARINEWIND Questionnaire: anonymous completion of an online questionnaire and visualisation and discussion of the results in real time with the aim of analysing the barriers to and opportunities for implementing FOW projects in Portugal – Co-creation activity moderated by Inês Machado, Marine Environment and Licensing Coordinator - WavEC Offshore Renewables, and Filipa Madureira, Communication Assistant – WavEC Offshore Renewables.

16:25-16:30 Closing and Coffee Break

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT:

Figure 1 shows the target audience for the 2nd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (108 invitations), and Figure 2 shows the final audience that participated in the event (25 participants).

Figure 1. Initial target audience for the 2nd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (Viana do Castelo).

Figure 2. Participants of the 2nd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (Viana do Castelo).

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 Relevance of the topics addressed in the 2nd Workshop in Portugal in the national floating offshore wind context

The current energy policy framework in Portugal aims to achieve a balanced energy supply, environmental sustainability, and economic feasibility, putting a strong emphasis on harnessing offshore wind resources to achieve these goals. This commitment is exemplified by the successful Windfloat and Windfloat Atlantic projects, which demonstrated the viability of semi-submersible technology in Portugal. The first initiative was a full-scale pilot project, a collaboration between EDP and Principle Power Inc. (PPI), featuring a 2 MW wind turbine mounted on a semi-submersible floating platform developed by PPI. It was installed in 2011 off the coast of Póvoa de Varzim, proving the viability of this technology. This success led to the pre-commercial Windfloat Atlantic project, the world's first semi-submersible offshore wind farm, installed in 2019 off the coast of Viana do Castelo. With a total capacity of 25 MW, consisting of three turbines each with a nominal power of 8.4 MW, Windfloat Atlantic not only set a significant precedent for semi-submersible technology but also spurred the development of an emerging offshore energy cluster in Portugal.

Given recent technological advances in floating offshore wind, in which Portugal has played a leading role, the Portuguese government aims to achieve an installed capacity of 2 GW and 10 GW auctioned of floating offshore wind by 2030 and 2050, respectively. This target is part of broader goals to decarbonize the economy and energy sector by 2050, to increase the contribution of renewable energies in electricity production to at least 85% by 2050, to develop an offshore renewable energy market with high potential for economic and social development of coastal areas, and to seek a stable production mix by combining offshore wind with other existing technologies in Portugal, offering highly competitive prices for consumers.

Given recent technological advances in floating offshore wind, in which Portugal has played a leading role, the Portuguese government aims to achieve an installed capacity of 2 GW and 10 GW auctioned of floating offshore wind by 2030 and 2050, respectively. This target is part of broader goals to decarbonize the economy and energy sector by 2050, to increase the contribution of renewable energies in electricity production to at least 85% by 2050, to develop an offshore renewable energy market with high potential for economic and social development of coastal areas, and to seek a stable production mix by combining offshore wind with other existing technologies in Portugal, offering highly competitive prices for consumers. The decision to pursue 2 GW of floating technologies through auctions by 2030 has been limited by the costs associated with the infrastructure development more precisely the investment in updating the in-grid infrastructure, which would likely cause a burden in the electricity bill of the public. On the other hand, the decision of installing 10 GW until 2050 is influenced by the constraints of the Portuguese continental shelf. Its narrow width and rapid depth increase near the coastline make it unfeasible to install wind farms with conventional fixed foundations, typically placed at depths ranging from 30 to 60 meters.

The Portuguese government has given firm steps towards the publication of the offshore wind auctions since the first semester of 2023. The most relevant advances are:

- **May 2023:** Presentation of the 1st Report by the Offshore Working Group to plan and operationalize renewable energy centres from oceanic resources in response to the climate crisis.
- **Oct 2023:** A period was opened for expressions of interest in participating in a competitive procedure for the development of offshore renewable projects (49 entities expressed interest).
- **Jan-Feb 2024:** First session of the dialogue and clarification phase.
- **Mar 2024:** Creation of the Mission Unit for the Licensing of Renewable Energy Projects 2030 (UMER 2030) with the objective of simplifying administrative procedures and introducing an online licensing system to accelerate the development of renewable energy projects.
- **Apr 2024:** Legal decree tasking REN with preparing a new proposal for the Development and Investment Plan for the Electricity Transmission Network (PDIRT-E) for the period 2024-2033.
- **Jul 2024:** Revised version of the National Energy and Climate Plan (PNEC) available for public consultation, aiming to align national energy and climate goals; indicating 2 GW of offshore wind installed capacity by 2030.

Even though the key authorities to support the licensing process of the development of offshore wind energy projects are well defined (DGEG - General Directorate for Energy and Geology, responsible for issuing the Reserve Capacity Title (TRC), the production license and the operation license; DGRM – General Directorate for Natural Resources, responsible for issuing the titles for Private Use of the Maritime Space (TUPEM); APA – Portuguese Environment Agency, responsible for the EIA), the existing regulatory framework does not contain specific provisions for floating offshore wind farms. However, following recent indications by the European Union Net-Zero Industry Act (NZIA), the Portuguese Government has mandated the creation of a Working Group, formed to work towards the Permitting and Licensing of Renewable Energy Projects – Estratégia de Missão para as Energias Renováveis (EMER 2030). The aim is to establish a One-Stop-Shop, centralizing all procedures and ensuring faster and transparent permitting workflows.

The MARINEWIND project aims to assess each country Labs context in terms of barriers and opportunities for floating offshore wind energy projects. Given that the Portuguese Government is on the verge of publishing the rules for its first competitive auction for commercial offshore wind development, it is crucial to understand how the auction's design, particularly the inclusion of non-price criteria, will impact the engagement and development of these projects in Portugal. This topic prompted the organization of the 2nd Workshop in Portugal.

2.2 Results of the Presentation “Applying pre-qualification criteria to offshore wind energy auctions in Portugal to boost the supply chain and promote biodiversity and marine ecosystems in Portugal”

The presentation made by Inês Machado covered several key areas related to the competitive procedures towards the commercial development of floating offshore wind energy in Portugal. It began by setting the scene of the current political and legal framework in Portugal, detailing the relevant policies and regulations at both the European Union and national (Portuguese) levels. The discussion then shifted to non-price criteria, which are becoming increasingly important in the

evaluation of offshore wind energy projects, the importance of developing a robust local supply chain to support the offshore wind sector, and, finally, the environmental and social challenges associated with floating offshore wind energy.

To analyze the political and legal framework, the presentation introduced the audience to the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA), approved in December 2023. The NZIA aims to promote the European industry manufacturing technologies and/or strategic components to achieve climate neutrality, where onshore and offshore wind technologies are considered strategic technologies. Article 20 of the NZIA sets out criteria to be adopted by Member States in competitive procedures and focuses on public procurement with the best quality-price ratio, including contributions to sustainability and resilience. According to this article, these procedures must include pre-qualification criteria such as responsible business conduct, cybersecurity and data protection, and capacity to complete the project within the stipulated timeframe.

Additionally, the criteria for sustainability and resilience must be cumulative, objective, transparent, and non-discriminatory and shall include contribution to sustainability and resilience, environmental sustainability beyond the minimum legal requirements, innovation, and contribution to the integration of the energy system. The contribution to sustainability and resilience should account for 15% to 30% of the awarding criteria in competitive procedures, with flexibility for greater weighting, although considerations of sustainability and resilience can be exempt if the procurement involves disproportionate costs or technical challenges.

Another important document recently published in October 2023 by the European Commission was the European Wind Power Action Plan. This document also highlights the importance of non-price criteria during pre-qualification and auction phases. They shall be well-designed, objective, transparent, and non-discriminatory, aiming to reward higher value-added products, promote industrial scalability, extend the lifespan of installations, implement carbon content or circular economy measures, and address the risk of project delays or non-execution.

The Portuguese government is considering two models for the offshore wind auctions: 1) the Unified Centralized Model and, 2) the Sequential Centralized Model. Both models share auction schedule for the allocation of TUPEM and TRC/CfD – Contracts for Difference (including areas, volumes, base price), and the allocation of TRC including definition of grid connection point and provision of electrical infrastructure. The main difference between the two models is that, for the Unified Model, there is a simultaneous allocation of TUPEM and TRC/CfD, whereas for the Sequential Model there is a sequential allocation of TUPEM and TRC/CfD. This difference led to field studies carried out without guaranteeing the award of TRC, CfD or TUPEM in the first model that will promote potential collaborations between developers to conduct field studies. After the granting of the TRC, the necessary actions must be taken in order to achieve the production license and a favourable environmental title. For the Sequential Model, field studies will be carried out with guaranteed allocation of TUPEM and the admission to CfD auctions will be subjected to project compliance of pre-qualification criteria.

The pre-qualification criteria will be the same regardless the adopted model and its objective is assessing the promoters' technical and financial capacity. Promoters must demonstrate cumulative proficiency in the development of offshore wind projects by proving track record in offshore wind

energy maintenance and operation, established experience in developing renewable energy projects, strong portfolio of liquid assets, and minimum liquidity requirement, amongst other requirements. For these important pre-qualification criteria, the limits for the different criteria are still under discussion but will be aligned according to the feedback gathered from stakeholders.

During the auction phase, in addition to the price criteria, the promoters must demonstrate cumulative proficiency in promoting the supply chain (resilience), environmental sustainability, innovation, all non-price criteria. Special emphasis will be given in Portugal for the promotion of the Portuguese supply chain and the environmental sustainability. The weight of these criteria will be aligned according to the indications given by the European Commission.

Regarding the supply chain, Portugal's established onshore wind technology industry and strong metallurgical and cement sectors provide a solid foundation for developing offshore projects and their value chains. Portuguese ports have received several offers from companies seeking to set up operations, presenting an export opportunity due to numerous global offshore projects. However, the embryonic stage of the floating offshore wind energy industry needs significant effort and investment by authorities to establish a competitive industrial cluster in the country. To support offshore wind project development, strategies are needed to increase the capacity of the national naval industry and foster dedicated training plans and R&D partnerships between universities and companies.

As mentioned above, promoting sustainability will be essential for the new floating offshore wind projects in Portugal. Criteria for sustainable FOWTs will include environmental impact assessment (EIA), mitigation measures that imply technological innovations and operational solutions to minimize the impact, compensation and restoration measures, cumulative impact assessment, and circularity of materials. For offshore projects, the EIA assessment is required for power capacity above 50 MW or for more than 20 turbines' project, or above 20 MW or 10 turbines if localized in sensitive areas. Implementing mitigation measures will be necessary, but also it is encouraged to include in the projects measures to strengthen the ecosystem through the design of wind farms. The latest can be done by optimizing the infrastructure to enhance habitats for native species or restoration.

To conclude the presentation, the following main recommendations for the offshore wind Portuguese auctions were discussed with the audience:

- 1) Ensure that non-price criteria are transparent, quantifiable, and straightforward.
- 2) Integrate resilience assessment criteria for critical equipment in FOW farms to safeguard the resilience of the supply chain.
- 3) Incorporate environmental sustainability criteria through inclusive designs that promote the circular economy, including the shortening of supply chains.
- 4) Promote coexistence with other sectors of the blue economy, such as offshore aquaculture.
- 5) Consider social and territorial development criteria, promoting the involvement of stakeholders.

2.3 Presentation of the European MARINEWIND project

The presentation of the MARINEWIND project was conducted by Janete Correia (WavEC). The following topics were included and presented during this part of the event:

- Promotional MARINEWIND video
- Composition of the MARINEWIND Consortium.
- Ambition of the project.
- Methodology and duration of the project.
- Location of the 5 Labs (Portugal, UK, Greece, Italy, and Spain), highlighting the importance of the different developing phases in the implementation of FOWTs of each country, and how it is expected that Labs will support the transfer of knowledge from the established experiences to the potential FOWT sites where plans for installation of FOWT are still at various stages of planning or implementation.
- Presentation of the most relevant projects or initiatives of each Lab.
- Presentation of the progress of the MARINEWIND Project (main public deliverables to be available soon on the website, number of workshops conducted until May 2024, etc.)
- Introduction to the Co-creation activity in the MENTIMETER Tool.

3 CO-CREATION ACTIVITY

A survey was prepared by APRE, RSE, CNR and UoY on the MENTIMETER Tool to be submitted to all the participants during the three Workshop events of the MARINEWIND Labs. This data collection exercise was intended to provide an insightful data of participants' experiences and insights regarding barriers and enablers for the implementation of floating offshore wind in Portugal.

This activity was included and designed in the 2nd Co-creation Workshop in Portugal to encourage the formulation of additional questions to the audience, to broaden the discussion on the barriers and opportunities facing the floating wind energy market in Portugal and other relevant information about Portugal in the context of the European MARINEWIND project.

3.1 Results of the survey

Question 1 - Which of the following categories represents you?

Figure 3. MENTIMETER Tool Question 1 results.

The first question aimed to give a figurative representation of the audience in the room answering this questionnaire. Based on the 21 answers collected, we can say that 62% of the people answering this questionnaire come from the Associations and Business sectors. Universities represent 19% of the audience, while Institutions (14%) and Research Entities (5%) represent the missing 19% of the audience.

Question 2 - What are the most important enabling factors to invest in FOWTs?

Figure 4. MENTIMETER Tool Question 2 results.

This question received votes from 21 participants. A “Clear regulatory framework” and the “Potential for local supply chain development” were the answers with more votes representing 48% of the total number of votes, with 24% each. In the third place is the “Presence of incentives” with 19% of the votes. The “Large market share and demand”, the “Technological maturity (platform, dynamic cables)” and the “Stability of the national transmission grid” represent the other 33%.

Question 3 - In your opinion, which of these risks is most significant to your value chain?

Figure 5. MENTIMETER Tool Question 3 results.

The “development of adequate infrastructures (e.g., ports)” was the most significant risk associated with the value chain chosen by the audience with 13 votes out of 16 (81%). “Local level supply chain

capacity” received the remaining votes, representing 19% once no one voted on “Availability of ad hoc vessels for the installation of the turbines”.

Question 4 - How can the industry engage with local communities and stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of FOWTs? Prioritise the actions.

Figure 6. MENTIMETER Tool Question 4 results.

In this question, the audience was asked to order, by the level of importance, the actions that could help the industry to engage with the local communities and stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of FOWTs. With 21 answers, the final order revealed that people consider promoting inclusive decision-making the most effective action. “Establishing partnerships with local and public organisations” got the second place followed by “Propose biodiversity recovery plans, environmental benefits and safety measures!”, “Inform the local community about FOWT financial benefits (e.g. new job opportunities)”, “Implement community outreach & educational programmes (e.g. workshops, lectures)”, “Update the local community about the pilot results (e.g. platforms, prototypes)” and “Share environmental and socioeconomic studies”.

Question 5 - What are the key environmental concerns associated with FOWTs?

Figure 7. MENTIMETER Tool Question 5 results.

In this question, which allowed each person to choose one to three options, were identified three key environmental concerns associated with FOWTs: “Impact on marine ecosystems (e.g. reduction of

biodiversity)” with 18 votes, “Habitat degradation/modification” with 16 votes, and “Noise, electromagnetic fields, heat, pollution” with 12 votes. These three environmental risks collected 78% of the votes, while “Sediment resuspension” did not get any votes and “Possible spills” got only one vote.

Question 6 - What infrastructure challenges need to be addressed to support the growth of the floating offshore wind energy industry?

Figure 8. MENTIMETER Tool Question 6 results.

Like the previous question, here each person was allowed to choose one to three options. Again, there were three clear winners regarding infrastructure challenges that need to be addressed to support the growth of the FOW sector in Portugal: “Invest in adequate port infrastructures for the logistics, installation and maintenance phases” with 15 votes, “Scalability of current solutions to commercial scale” with 12 votes, and “Technological maturity” with 10 votes. These three challenges represented 66% of the total number of votes, while “Invest in piloting and testing phases” and “Stability of the electrical network” only received 2 votes each.

Question 7 - What strategies can be employed to build trust and acceptance among communities where these technologies are being deployed?

Figure 9. MENTIMETER Tool Question 7 results.

In this question, again, each person was allowed to choose one to three options. 20 participants replied to the question “What strategies can be employed to build trust and acceptance among communities where these technologies are being deployed?” The answers with more votes were “Define fishing areas/zones” (12) and “Foster public participation” (11), followed by “Increase environmental studies”

(9), “Encourage and support local businesses to provide operations and maintenance solutions” and Minimize sea use and co-existing conflicts (7 each), “Propose biodiversity recovery plans” and Implement benefit-sharing mechanisms (6 each) and “Develop metrics to assess participation and make these part of project evaluations” (1).

Question 8 - Which activity is the most conflicting with the offshore wind sector?

Figure 10. MENTIMETER Tool Question 8 results.

Regarding which activity is most conflicting with the offshore wind sector, “fishing” got the first place, followed by “environmental protection”, which was closely followed by “shipping”. “Tourism” came in fourth place.

Question 9 - Which activity is most compatible with the floating offshore wind sector?

Figure 11. MENTIMETER Tool Question 9 results.

In this question, the audience was asked to score each option, from zero to ten, in accordance with its compatibility with the FOW sector. When asked about “Which activity is most compatible with the floating offshore wind sector?”, the audience agreed that “Tourism” is the most compatible, followed by “Shipping” and “Environmental protection”. The less compatible activity chosen is “Fishing” and “Other”.

Question 10 - What kind of impact do you think floating offshore wind farms could have on local economic activities (e.g., fishing, tourism)?

Figure 12. MENTIMETER Tool Question 10 results.

When participants were asked about the kind of impact of floating offshore wind farms on local economic activities, 20 attendees replied the following: “Strong positive impact” (7), “Positive impact” (4), “Strong negative impact” (4), “Moderate positive impact” (2), “Negative impact” (1), “Moderate negative impact” (1) and “Neutral impact” (1)

Question 11 - What kind of impact do you think floating offshore wind farms could have on the environment (e.g., biodiversity)?

Figure 13. MENTIMETER Tool Question 11 results.

When participants were asked about the kind of impact of floating offshore wind farms on the environment, 20 attendees replied the following: “Neutral impact” (5), “Positive impact” and “Moderate negative impact” (4 each), “Moderate positive impact” and “Strong negative impact” (3 each), and “Strong positive impact” (1)

Question 12 - Do you think that floating offshore wind farms could bring benefits to the local community (e.g., economic benefits and energy savings, improvement of air quality, general improvement of quality of life)?

Figure 14. MENTIMETER Tool Question 12 results.

When participants were asked “Do you think that floating offshore wind farms could bring benefits to the local community?”, 21 attendees replied. The majority stated, “I agree completely” (9), followed by “I agree” (5). 3 attendees votes “I agree a little bit” and the rest voted: “Neutral” (1), “I disagree a little bit” (1), “I disagree” (1) and “I completely disagree” (1)

4 DISCUSSIONS TOPICS OVERVIEW

Inês Machado's presentation initiated a discussion on the future development of the offshore wind sector in Portugal. The workshop, attended by various stakeholders, included several fishermen's associations, making it a crucial platform to address their concerns. Given the significant changes proposed in the maritime environment, the primary focus was on understanding how this development might impact the livelihoods of fishermen and their communities. The presence of these associations underscored the importance of integrating their voices into the conversation.

Before WavEC introduced the Mentimeter questions, the fishermen had already begun to articulate their anxieties. They claimed that they had been approached on various occasions by different representatives interested in collaboration. However, despite their willingness to engage, they felt each interaction lacked follow-through. Concrete solutions were never offered, leading to a sense of frustration and disillusionment. This repeated pattern left their concerns unresolved and contributed to growing scepticism about the sincerity of these outreach efforts.

Initially, the fishermen were reluctant to engage with the new questions presented during the workshop. They expressed concerns that the questions seemed to be framed in a manner that predetermined the answers and did not adequately consider their specific challenges. This perception further alienated them, as they felt the questions sidestepped the core issues they faced daily.

The fact that the fishermen raised their voices before the Mentimeter session led to a somewhat subdued atmosphere among the other stakeholders. While all stakeholders replied to the questions, there was a noticeable lack of dynamic interaction between them and the fishermen. The presence of many fishermen's associations from the Viana do Castelo area, highlighted the local importance of the issues at hand. Despite the widespread participation, the session did not fully achieve a collaborative dialogue, underlining the need for better facilitation in future discussions.

However, once the organisers clarified that the questions were more directly related to their activities and concerns, the atmosphere changed significantly. The fishermen became very active in replying to the Mentimeter questions, engaging enthusiastically and providing valuable insights. This shift highlighted the importance of clear communication and the need to ensure that stakeholders feel their specific issues are being addressed. By fostering an environment of genuine dialogue, the workshop successfully tapped into the fishermen's expertise and perspectives, paving the way for more collaborative and effective future discussions.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the 2nd Workshop on the left column, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the right column. Some of the identified barriers and enablers were already identified during the 1st Workshop in Portugal.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
Foundations and turbines are the components that need the most urgent expansion in manufacturing.	Successful track record in national and international supply chain integration for the Windfloat Atlantic project.
Negative impact on tourism revenues.	Significant contribution to decarbonisation of the energy system.
Environmental concerns arising from the interaction of FOWTs with the marine environment – negative impacts.	New R&D-related activities in development of marine energies or monitoring of environmental aspects.
Need for pilot studies on the scalability of Nature (NID).	Job creation.
Opposition from fishing associations due to limited access to maritime areas.	Lower electricity rates.
Recreational navigation or sporting activities limited or affected.	Possibility of promoting other activities within a co-existence approach of the maritime space such as carbon capture, aquaculture, ocean monitoring and observation or environmental protection (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).
No experience with offshore wind energy auctions.	Recent advances in Portugal to create a clearer regulatory framework for the implementation of offshore wind projects (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).
The Maritime Spatial Plan (POEM) has recently been updated to include offshore wind energy areas (discussions ongoing).	Economic advantages for local and national enterprises of any direct participation in the supply chain (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).
New vessels for installing foundations need to be ordered approximately 3-4 years in advance.	National planning supporting the implementation of offshore wind energy on the

	medium and long term (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).
Non-availability of raw materials (copper, steel, etc.) can delay project delivery.	Environment sanctuaries that promote biodiversity created by wind farms when no other activities are allowed in the wind farm maritime space (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).
No territorial planning reconciling the interests of various sectors and eliminating possible conflicts (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).	
Lack of enough internal technical capacity to meet the future needs of the offshore wind industry (<i>identified too during the 1st Workshop</i>).	